

CENTROID OF THE ADDED MASS AND ITS EFFECTS ON GOVERNING EQUATIONS

Genick Bar–Meir

Potto Project

Skokie, Illinois 60076

Email: genick at potto dot org

ORCID: 0000-0003-3285-7837

ABSTRACT

The pivot points of surface vessels and submerged bodies are assumed to be at locations of body centre in research papers. Yet the actual pilots observations show that the rotation pivot (yaw) is at different location. Some researchers also observed that actual results are far from the actual result. This discrepancy is posted to the community yet no explanation was provided until this point.

The governing equations solved today are missing several elements to bring these equations closer to reality. At very least, when one solves the governing equations, one should know what terms they are neglecting (and why) and what assumptions were made. These missing elements are the solid body rotation locations, centroid of the actual added mass and the added moment of inertia. For the surface vehicles, the pivot point for the yaw is the only rotation to be determined while for the submerged bodies all the three rotations should be calculated. This discussion deals with the centroid of the added mass to help to determine the rotation hinge point.

NOMENCLATURE

a	acceleration
E	System energy
F	Force
\mathbb{M}	Added mass representative volume
m	The (body) mass
t	Time
U_0	Representative velocity of the fluid
u	Liquid velocity
V	Domain Volume
x	Distance in straight (movement) direction
y	Distance perpendicular to x

z Distance perpendicular to x and y

Greek Letters

ρ density

Subscript

i Number direction, x, y, z

ℓ liquid

Key Words

Ship Rotation Axes, Yaw, Roll, Pitch, Added Mass, Centre of the Added Mass, Marine Navigation, Fish Locomotion

1 Introduction

Observing that the marine navigation and motions of surface vehicles and submerged bodies attracted probably the best minds such as Bernoulli, Euler, and Darwin just to name a few. Yet, the field is like an onion in which after peeling totally a new approach which changes the undersigning. For example, the discovery (or invention) of buoyancy center lead to the definition of metacenter. At that time the rolling (one of the rotation of the ship) was calculated by ignoring the added moment of inertia. Of course, plentiful experimental evidence were provided to demonstrate that the solution is in perfect agreement with experiments.

Today these experimental evidence will cause researchers to chuckle. Nevertheless, currently the GATE (Graduate Aptitude Test in Engineering) still ignoring the added mass in the ship rolling calculations. This kind of muscle memory plagues the field in many respects. This confliction of geniuses is puzzling, yet it is a fact. The explanation why this confliction exist cannot be provided here, attempt to resolve it lead to peel another onion layer.

In (Bar-Meir 2023), the reasons and locations of the pivots of surface vehicle was established yet the centroid of the added mass was missing and it is needed to calculate the new rotation pivot. The survey of the literature show no reference to the centroid of the added of mass probably due to lack of understanding of the importance of this issue. The fact that no research was carried on the centroid of the added mass dictates why the situation occurred and has to be discussed.

The main point is that individuals such as Horace Lamb, J Newman who took the lead were with a strong mathematical point of view. This fact led to uni-direction potential which refers as the added mass coefficients. These coefficients have cloaked the fact that there is really only one and sole added mass. The body does not “know” that there many coefficients rather there is a single and only added mass which depends on the acceleration direction. Yet, the added mass is not a vector in the regular sense. This fact was discovered in (Bar-Meir 2022). The implication will be discussed in the following paper.

The transition from “ignoring the added mass” to the regular usage of the added mass was over 40 years (it is not completely went through the full transition). Even currently there are some researchers who confused the added mass with the pressure distribution on the ship or the body. Some papers in this category will be discussed blow. There are several approaches to tackle the added. The old approach to added mass problem was simply to ignore it. Example of such case is (Froude 1861) and it continue by textbooks like (Lester 2013) (Biran and López-Pulido 2013) etc. This old approach was replaced by the schizophrenic approach where the added mass (the matrix) is added to the governing equations and yet in the same time, the centre of the combined bodies remains as if the added mass does not exist like the initial approach (just ignore it for the calculation of ship centre). This approach is advocated by Fossen (2011), (Techet 2005) etc. In fact, the last method, there are additional violations of physical principles such as incorrect calculations of moment of inertia ship body etc.

Another example, Wang et al (2015) basically ignore the issue of the added mass (notice the numerical method is not the point here). Another method to address the added mass was proposed by Alberti et al (2023) concerned with the turbulence while neglecting the added mass (matrix). The added mass is not included in the calculations and probably it was replaced by the turbulence some how filling the gap. The replacement of the added mass with the turbulence regardless to the shape of the body seems strange. Hence, this work is an exercises in solving equations with turbulence but ignoring the added mass not a real solution to the physical situation. If one think that this confusion is sole example, consider Abbasi (2021) who study the combination of the heave and the pitch. Under these circumstances, the moment of inertia of yad movement changes drastically and the location of the pivot as well.

The subject “What is the added mass?” should be dis-

cussed here due to the common misconceptions are penetrating into the field. For example of such misconception is the statement (Limacher, Morton, and Wood 2018) by “[t]he concept of added mass arises from potential flow analysis and is associated with the acceleration of a body in an inviscid irrotational fluid. When shed vorticity is modeled as vortex singularities embedded in this irrotational flow, the associated force can be superimposed onto the added-mass force due to the linearity of the governing Laplace equation.” This example is analogous to comparing apple and oranges and stating that both have similar weight and some what similar volume and thus they are the same. The added mass is due to the resistance to the acceleration of the fluid around the body and it is actual physical phenomenon. The value of the added mass is oblivious to roughness of the body or its density. The vertices are function of Reynolds number and hence the vertices are a function of the viscosity (Reynolds depends on the viscosity). Yet, the added mass is not a function of the viscosity. The two phenomena are different and results are not equal since they depend strongly on two sets of different variables. The assumptions that Limacher et al made are simply wrong. The added mass is based on Re number equal infinity then, the vertices are a function of finite Reynolds number. The decomposition requires by this model several assumptions which some are wrong. For instance, the vertices also appear (hence force) when body is at constant velocity while the added **force** (the active added mass) is zero. Clearly, this difference contradicts each other phenomenon. Additionally the added mass is not the pressure integral around body. To demonstrate this point consider, a body at constant velocity and d’Alembert’s paradox is applied and thus no resistance. Yet, the added mass (even though there is no acceleration) exists regardless of the fact that the pressure integral is zero. Hence, the d’Alembert’s is not related to the added mass.

Since the previous work was published, several individuals alluded to several articles which were published previously by practitioners. The practical observation and understanding is that academia failed these pilots which can be illustrated by these articles. First even some academicians realize the current state of situations is wrong. For example, Rowe (1996) suggested that the pivot point theory which assumed rotation is based on forces. Later Seo (2016) tried to explain the “misconception”. Of course it followed by pilots who tried to explain their physical observations with what they see that the academia’s work has no legs in reality. The Seo’s explanation is based on the fact that the ship goes through sway and yaw in the same time. There will be a point where ship in the “new location (line)” will meet the old location (line). This location, according to the promoters of the pivoted point concept, is the pivot point of the ship. Nevertheless, the ship is not really rotated around this point and this point is continuously changing. It is hard to see why one consider this point to be the hinge point. Yet, this is very popular with pilots. For example, in two articles (Cummins 2020b) and (Cummins

2020a) explained his understanding on the pivot point. According to their experience the rotation point moves back or front depending on the direction of the acceleration and added elements such as a moving rudder (which is adding added mass). These pilots are not engineers who should be expected to be familiar with the added mass concepts. The reality is that added mass is a strange concept for most engineers not to say the general public such as the pilots. In fact, even “researchers” in the field have misconceptions about the added mass. The problem in these articles is the lack of knowledge that a body in isolation must rotate around its mass centre.

It is not that the researchers do not aware that their research represent the approach that ignore the added mass. The situation even at times stare at the researchers face and yet they are oblivious to the effect of the added mass. For example, Mansuy et al (2023) were discussing how well experienced pilots were selected to conduct the experiments and they compared their techniques with their simulations. The core of the experiments was to navigate a two bents river segment. These pilots described several techniques they used to change the added mass of the surface vehicles such as changing the angle of rudder. These changes of the added mass used to navigate utilizing different pivot points. The researchers did not question why the pilots done their actions which change the added mass .

2 The Method of Calculations of The Added Mass

The combined ship centre and the added mass centroid are required to find the pivot point of the body. This combination is the whole system. The mass centre of the ship is well established and there are many techniques to obtain it (Bar-Meir 2021). Hence no discussion is offered on this point. Yet, previously no one tackles the problem of the centroid of the added mass that this author aware of. The approach taken here is to use the method that typically used in body centroid and other situations. This unsophisticated, direct, and crude method might not be the best method and others are invited to improve this proposed method.

The typical notation of the ship motions is exhibited in fig. 1. While the pitch and roll rotations have predetermined pivot points the yaw still has to be determined for surface vehicles. For aquatic bodies or submerged bodies all the three rotations should be considered and determined. The derivations of the standard linear added mass is repeated from the previous discussion (Bar-Meir 2022) for completeness. The kinetic energy in the field is

$$E = \frac{\rho_l}{2} \int_V ((u_1)^2 + (u_2)^2 + (u_3)^2) dV \quad (1)$$

where here E denotes the energy of the entire field and u_1 is the locale velocity in let say x the same for the other components (u_2 velocity in y and u_3 velocity in z or any other orthogonal coordi-

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FIGURE 1. The common names for the ship movements.

nate system). Note, this statement is correct for any orthogonal system. The velocity of the body is denoted as U_0 and can be pulled out the integral as

$$E = \frac{\rho_l (U_0)^2}{2} \int_V \left(\left(\frac{u_1}{U_0} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{u_2}{U_0} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{u_3}{U_0} \right)^2 \right) dV \quad (2)$$

This operation is carried out to relate velocity field and the body velocity. This operation has the advantage of solving only for a body with one unit of velocity. Now, there is no need to solve the equation for all velocities. The integral can be written as

$$\mathbb{M} = \int_V \left(\left(\frac{u_1}{U_0} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{u_2}{U_0} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{u_3}{U_0} \right)^2 \right) dV \quad (3)$$

The value of the integral eq. (3) is independent of the body velocity and therefore every geometry and ordination can be evaluated. The kinetic energy of the fluid field is

$$E = \frac{\rho_l U_0^2}{2} \mathbb{M} \quad (4)$$

The derivative with respect to the time of \mathbb{M} is zero (or in other words, the added mass is fixed). This statement is correct for translation motion. Furthermore, if the velocity is made of only one component like u_x then the added mass coefficient is obtained. Note in that case, the added mass coefficient has to multiply by the velocity component. The derivative of eq. (4) utilizing the chain rule yields

$$\frac{dE}{dt} = \rho U_0 \mathbb{M} \frac{dU_0}{dt} \quad (5)$$

The power required to be supplied to the field to carry this change has to be

$$power = F U_0 \quad (6)$$

The energy conservation requires that the power supplied has to be equal to the change of the kinetic energy of the field where here, F is the force and U is the velocity, hence

$$F U_0 = \frac{dE}{dt} = \rho_\ell U_0 \mathbb{M} \frac{dU}{dt} \quad (7)$$

Canceling the velocity on both sides of eq. (7) provides

$$F = \rho_\ell \mathbb{M} \frac{dU}{dt} \quad (8)$$

Equation (8) can obtain the standard of form $F = ma$ when $\rho_\ell \mathbb{M}$ are combination and denoted as the added mass. This added mass is not actual the liquid mass but rather a representation of equivalent mass if it would be accelerated with the body. A entire fluid field is accelerated but not in the same way neither in an uniformly or the actual amount. So, instead of doing the calculations for the entire field it is done for a simpler representation is utilized. Equation (8) is constructed in the current way where the added mass remains constant and thus it requires that the acceleration to be the same direction. Or in a different way, this definition refers to the absolute direction (and thus the velocity fraction as well, if the total direction remains the same.).

3 The Added Mass

As it was stated previously, the typical body centroid template will be used (no weight function).

$$\bar{x}_i = \frac{\int_V x_i \left(\left(\frac{u_1}{U_0} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{u_2}{U_0} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{u_3}{U_0} \right)^2 \right) dV}{\int_V \left(\left(\frac{u_1}{U_0} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{u_2}{U_0} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{u_3}{U_0} \right)^2 \right) dV} \quad (9)$$

For symmetrical bodies, the integral in the numerator vanishes. It worth to note that symmetry is required also for the mass (weight) distribution as well. Thus, when evaluating the integral, there is always a counter element for every elements on the other side for symmetrical shapes. Thus, the centroid of the **mass** must aligned with the centre of the body **volume**. Conversely, bodies that are not symmetrical, the centroid of the added mass has

a value which can be very large. For example, the added mass centroid of the ellipsoid is at the ellipsoid centroid (when the ellipsoid is made of an uniform material). It does not matter that the ellipsoid is moving in an angle of attack. The integral will be vanishing regardless for any the angle of attack. From a physical and mathematical point of view, when carrying out the integration it can be noticed that there is always a canceling element. However, if this ellipsoid will have a rudder, the added mass centroid will change when a rudder is pointing either to the left or to right (regardless to the acceleration). Note that in this case, yaw will be rotating closer to the stern (back of the ship).

If a symmetrical body shape has a density distribution such as actual fish body centre is not located in the volume centroid. The pivot point of this body requires a different moment of inertia. For example, for ellipsoid that has a body distribution such that mass centre is not at ellipsoid centroid (volume center) then the pivot point is at the centre. However when adding (or subtracting) the added mass it moves the pivot of the combined system closer ellipsoid centroid. In this analysis, this point becomes clearer even though no calculations were made. Note, in many ships, the engine is at the stern (back) of the ship hence the pivot point tends to be at the back. However, if the ship was symmetrical then the pivot is at centre of the ship. Notice no one in literature presented this analysis or even consider it.

As oppose commonly believed, the added moment of inertia of yaw is not a constant number but rather and a function of the draft (depth) and trim among other parameters. To be more specific, the heave (up or down movement or change of the draft) causes change of the value of the yaw added moment of inertia. Notice, the sway (side to side or the surge) does not have any effect on the yaw added moment of inertia. For submerged bodies, the (translation) linear motions (heave, sway, surge) do not effect the moment of inertia as first approximation. The change of the moment of inertia is due to the changing of the body shape.

The flat-earthers had a hard time to explain where is the edge of the world. None of them ever seen the edge and yet they ridiculed those who believe that earth is a sphere. One search for the ship pivot point on the web site with the answer as “[t]he pivot point is considered to be the centre of leverage for forces acting on the ship. The pivot point is generally at 1/3 ship’s length from the bow when the ship is moving ahead, and between 1/4 ship’s length from the stern and the rudder post when going astern.” (United Kingdom Maritime Pilots’ Association). One cannot expect or should expect these fellows to be expert on added mass and centre of combined bodies but for navigation they much better feel than those who invented of the GMM from Japan or other “scientific” ideas which are not based on science.

4 The Large Pivot Point

The common method to confuse others is to refer to two different items that are some what similar in the same name. In this case,

there two different kind pivot points: one) in which the ship is rotating around (pivot point), and two) the ship hypothetical point far from the ship around which appear to rotate (the large pivot point). The main difference between these two pivot points, aside that they are in different locations, is that one deals the oscillating ship (yaw) while the large pivot point deals with navigation around the ship. Additionally, the pivot point deals with the real rotation point while the large pivot is only approximated as a rotation Zinchenko (2023). The combination of a linear movement with a rotation is not a pure rotation with a clear pivot in stationary coordinates. When force (a tugboat for example) is applied to a ship, the ship will have a force and moment applied to it. Thus, the ship will rotate and will move linearly (translation motion). This combination under certain circumstance can be approximated as rotation. This issue is mentioned here just to point to existence of the other pivot point.

Concluding Remarks

In this paper the missing point (added mass centroid) in previous paper was addressed and defined. Additional points on the symmetry body and their effects on the centroid were discussed. It is hoped that individuals will start to build the tables with added mass and its centroid for various geometries. Hence papers like (Russo 2006) published to state that science is not working should be have the need to appear. Russo is right because what people were doing is not real science.

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About the Author

As opposed to many other researchers, this author does not brag about how many citations his work has or jobs he held but only points to how many breakthroughs he has made. In the die casting industry, he has revolutionized the field by solving several major open questions. These questions include the critical plunger velocity, pQ^2 diagram, intensification pressure and critical vent area etc (for those who not familiar with die casting, these are the main pliers of die casting.). It has to be mentioned that the die casting establishment believed in solutions which violated the second law of the thermo and has spent millions promoting these beliefs (like the woke religion). Since the problems were not solved, literally hundreds of CFD teams from all over the world attempted to solve the problem in vain where this author solved them. The establishment fought against publishing

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these discoveries. The irony is that these author's models today are undisputed and accepted in the industry.

Furthermore, the author solved several open problems in shock dynamics and potential of compressed substances. Additionally, this author solved the deep ocean pressure and speed of sound which many oceanographers failed to calculate (Pushka Equation). The ship stability went major revision and basically revamped the field in particular the added mass (properties). The old governing equations yielding hundreds percent errors had to be modified due to discoveries of this author.

Conflict of Interest

The author Genick Bar–Meir certify that he has NO affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity or person with any financial interest (such as honoraria; educational grants; participation in speakers bureaus; membership, employment, consultancies, stock ownership, or other equity interest; and expert testimony or patent–licensing arrangements), or non-financial interest (such as personal or professional relationships, affiliations, knowledge or beliefs) in the subject matter or materials or individuals discussed in this manuscript.

Genick Bar–Meir **ORCID:** 0000-0003-3285-7837

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